

STUDY ON IN-SITU SYNTHESIZED MAGNESIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Magnesium matrix composites were successfully synthesized by spontaneously infiltrating molten magnesium alloy into Al-Ti-C preforms and in situ forming TiC particles in the liquid of magnesium alloy. The results showed that compressive properties and damping capacities of magnesium matrix composites were effectively improved.

Keywords: magnesium matrix composites, in situ formation, TiC, microstructure, mechanical properties, damping properties.

INTRODUCTION

In the past few years, magnesium alloys are increasingly used for engineering components in the automobile industry. It offers a great potential for reducing the weight of a vehicle and thus raising fuel efficiency. However, the use of magnesium alloys has been limited because of the poor mechanical properties [1].

Magnesium matrix composites can combine the ductility, toughness and damping capacity of the magnesium matrix with the high strength and high modulus characteristics of the ceramic particles. With the development of magnesium matrix composites, it is possible to synthesize the new materials with both excellent mechanical properties and high damping capacity.

Traditionally, Mg-MMCs have been produced by *ex situ* methods. Compared to the conventional MMCs produced by *ex situ* methods, the *in situ* MMCs exhibit the finer reinforcement in size, more uniform distribution in the matrix, cleaner reinforcement-matrix interface and stronger interfacial bonding than *ex situ* one [2]. Among widely used reinforcements, TiC ceramic particles are attractive because of their many desirable properties, such as high hardness, low density, high modulus and high wear resistance.

In present work, molten magnesium alloy was spontaneously infiltrated into Al-Ti-C preforms, simultaneously the *in situ* reaction happened and TiC particles were formed in the liquid of magnesium alloy. Microstructure of *in situ* synthesized magnesium matrix composites has been investigated. Compressive mechanical properties and damping properties of TiC/AZ91D composites was further discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The preforms were made from commercial powders of Ti, Al and C. The powders were mixed in a ball mill filled with argon gas for 1h and then pressed into preforms. The compacted preforms were placed at the bottom of a steel crucible with commercial AZ91D magnesium alloys on it. The preforms and magnesium alloys were heated to 750°C under the protection of argon and held for about 30 min. After that, the temperature was reduced slowly to the mushy zone between 555°C and 570°C. The molten magnesium alloy was stirred with a graphite stirrer for 30 min to assist the dispersion of the particles. The melts were then heated to 750°C and cast into steel mould preheated to 250°C.

The microstructures of the composites were examined under MEF4M optical microscope (OM). The formation of new phases was monitored using D/max 2550V X-ray diffraction (XRD) with $\text{CuK}\alpha$. Transmission electron microscope (TEM) was employed to study the interface of particle/matrix. The compressive deformation behaviours were carried out on Gleeble-3500 machine. Damping capacity was measured on a Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (IDMA2980).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the Mg-Al-Ti-C system, from the viewpoint of thermodynamics TiC reinforced magnesium matrix composites can be fabricated successfully. Ti may directly react with C to form TiC. It is also possible that Ti may react with Al to form TiAl_3 in the initial stage, and then C may react with TiAl_3 to form TiC.

The results of X-ray diffraction (XRD) confirm the presence of TiC in composites. Optical micrographs of the composites reinforced with different volume fraction of TiC show that the distribution of reinforcements is nearly uniform in the matrix. With the increasing of the volume fraction of reinforcements, more TiC particles are observed to spread along the grain boundaries with $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$ eutectic phase and inside the primary magnesium grains.

Using present fabrication technique, molten magnesium alloy was spontaneously infiltrated into Al-Ti-C preforms and TiC particles were formed *in situ* in the liquid of magnesium alloy. Then the semisolid slurry stirring technique is used to facilitate the incorporation and uniform distribution of TiC particles in molten magnesium. The synthesis processes, such as preheat of Al-Ti-C preforms, preparation of TiC-Al master alloy and adding the master alloy into the molten magnesium, was simplified. So there is no contamination and oxidation induced, which is inevitable when the master alloy is put into the molten magnesium.

The compressive deformation behaviors of TiC reinforced Mg-MMCs were further investigated by means of uniaxial compression tests at strain rates between 10^{-3}s^{-1} and 1s^{-1} and temperature between room temperature and $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Early fracture was observed in the low-temperature/high strain rate regime, fracture occurring by crack propagation at 45 degree with respect to the compression axis. In high-temperature/low strain rate regime, the flow curves exhibited the typical flow softening shape. The results show that with the addition of TiC particles Mg-MMCs can effectively improve compressive properties of magnesium matrix at testing temperature interval. When compared to the unreinforced counterpart, TiC reinforced Mg-MMCs need higher temperature and lower strain rate to avoid premature fracture.

Damping capacities of *in situ* TiC reinforced Mg-MMCs with different reinforcement percentage were investigated. Experimental results show: TiC reinforced magnesium matrix composites have better damping capacities than that of non-reinforced magnesium alloy. Damping capacities of Mg-MMCs increased with the increase of TiC particles volume percentage. Compared to magnesium matrix alloy, an increase in damping capacities of TiC reinforced Mg-MMCs can be attributed to the dislocation damping mechanism at room temperature. At elevated temperatures, interface damping will be a new contributor to the increase of damping capacity.

References

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